

RECENT ADVANCES IN EMERGING NANOMATERIALS FOR THE DIAGNOSIS AND TREATMENT OF RHEUMATOID ARTHRITIS

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ABSTRACT

Rheumatoid arthritis (RA) is a relentless inflammatory disorder characterized by joint inflammation, synovial destruction, pannus formation, and the consequential erosion of bones and cartilage. Patients often endure persistent arthritic pain, swelling, stiffness, and functional impairment. The emergence of nanotechnology has opened new avenues for both diagnosing and treating RA, offering a holistic approach to address the intricate challenges associated with managing this condition. Understanding the intricate mechanisms and microenvironment of RA is crucial for developing effective diagnostic and therapeutic strategies. Common diagnostic techniques include imaging modalities such as X-rays and magnetic resonance imaging (MRI), as well as blood tests that measure specific biomarkers indicative of RA. Conventional therapeutic drugs for RA aim to suppress inflammation and modify the disease course, but they are not without drawbacks, including side effects and varying degrees of efficacy. Nanotechnology introduces innovative solutions for RA management. Drug-carrying nanoparticles present a promising avenue, facilitating targeted drug delivery to inflamed joints while minimizing systemic side effects. Photothermal therapy (PTT) and photodynamic therapy (PDT) represent cutting-edge approaches. PTT utilizes light-absorbing agents to generate localized heat, alleviating inflammation, while PDT involves light-activated compounds to induce cell death in inflamed tissues. These nanotherapy strategies offer potential advantages over traditional approaches. They enhance drug efficacy, minimize side effects, and provide targeted treatment, optimizing the balance between therapeutic benefits and potential risks. However, challenges such as biocompatibility, long-term safety, and scalability need careful consideration in their implementation. The integration of nanotechnology in diagnosing and treating RA offers a multifaceted approach to address the complexities of this chronic inflammatory condition. As research in this field advances, the potential for more effective, targeted, and personalized therapies for RA patients becomes increasingly promising, marking a transformative era in rheumatological care.

KEYWORDS: Nanomedicine, Nanotheranostics, Nanotherapeutics, Rheumatoid Arthritis, Targeted Drug Delivery

1. INTRODUCTION

Arthritis is defined as the inflammation of one or more joints (Y. Chow *et al.*, 2020), with various signs and symptoms such as joint redness, swelling, discomfort, and warmth (J. Y. Ng *et al.*, 2020). The two most common forms of arthritis are rheumatoid arthritis (RA) and osteoarthritis (OA)(T. Woo *et al.*, 2017). Rheumatoid arthritis is the most common autoimmune disease that affects the joints (I. B. McInnes *et al.*, 2011). This disease is associated with progressive disability, systemic complications, early death, and socioeconomic costs (G. S. Firestein *et al.*, 2003). This results in long-term impairment, inability to interact effectively in social life and daily employment, and greater death rates, all of which have a significant influence on the patient's quality of life (E. A. Littlejohn *et al.*, 2018). The inflammatory response, predominantly in RA, deals with immune cells such as macrophages, neutrophils, and T cells, which secrete a large number of pro-inflammatory cytokines and also generate reactive oxygen species that cause structural damage to cartilage and weaken the functional ability in the arthritic area. Due to the breakdown of bone and cartilage, joint swelling, and discomfort, this chronic autoimmune inflammatory disease limits movement and lowers quality of life. The relevance of RA diagnosis and therapy is critical because obtaining an accurate, early diagnosis of RA can be challenging, while the lack thereof can be detrimental to RA treatment. Many disease-modifying anti-rheumatic drugs such as methotrexate, dexamethasone, tocilizumab, and others have been used to reduce joint inflammation and deformity. Even so, these drugs have not been proven helpful for patients due to their adverse effects following long-term use (Liang *et al.*, 2022). Biological agents are commonly prescribed for the treatment of RA. Despite their ability to slow the progression of the disease, these treatments carry potential side effects such as NSAID-induced nephrotoxicity, liver damage, and heart failure (O. Kohler-Forsberg *et al.*, 2019)(P. Tziona *et al.*, 2017). In cases where medication proves ineffective, surgery becomes the only alternative (C. Maglio *et al.*, 2017),(B. Young *et al.*, 2018),(A. Ganhewa *et al.*, 2019). The quality of life for many patients has increased thanks to recent developments and novel treatment modalities that have significantly weakened disease progression (Dolati *et al.*, 2016).

The advancement of nanotechnology opens fresh perspectives for the study and treatment of RA. Using nanomaterials (NMs) as nanocarriers for drugs has enhanced their bioavailability and bioactivities and upgraded the selective targeting of inflamed joints. In addition, NMs' small size and considerable surface activity have enabled the controlled release of drugs that reduce their dose-dependent side effects. Combining diagnosis and treatment is the most effective strategy for managing the condition of RA patients. Recent research has demonstrated improved arthritis treatment via the employment of the combined effect of nanomaterial and photothermal therapy (Shang *et al.*, 2021). Nanotechnology has become a boom in the treatment of various inflammatory diseases. It has produced various tools in medical and biological research such as target drug delivery systems, numerous types of implants, and many types of diagnostic tools for the diagnosis of various types of diseases (Murthy *et al.*, 2006). Employing nanomaterials as carriers of chemical drugs, the water-

solubility, half-life, and sustained release behavior of these drugs are improved (D. D. patel *et al.*,). A variety of functional nanostructures such as liposomes, micelles, polymeric nanoparticles, dendrimers, nano gel and metallic nanoparticles are frequently used as drug delivery carriers for the fine control of RA treatment at specific sites such as inflammatory joints of RA patients. These delivery systems penetrate the epithelial barriers and release the drugs, and then these bioactive molecules move across multiple biological barriers to make it to the site of action(K. K. Jain *et al.*, 2008). An excellent drug delivery strategy ensures that an effective drug is bioavailable at the desired location (A. P. Singh *et al.*, 2019). The drug concentration at the target location should be within the therapeutic window, which is the range between the drug's minimum effective and hazardous concentrations (Y. Perrie *et al.*, 2012). Recent research has demonstrated improved arthritis treatment via the employment of the combined effect of nanomaterial and photothermal therapy (PTT). Among various NMs, polymer-based NMs act as vital photothermal reagents with high absorption in the near-infrared (NIR) region that can transform near-infrared light into localized heat, thus offering fewer side effects, easier integration with existing therapies, and increased effectiveness (Shang *et al.*, 2021). NMs with PTT can easily penetrate joint tissues without causing damage and facilitate imaging for an arthritis diagnosis. Recently, manifold works have been carried out that have revealed the efficiency of the combinatory effect of polymer-based NMs and PTT concerning the treatment and diagnosis of RA.(Zhang *et al.*, 2021).

2. PATHOGENESIS OF RA

The pathogenesis of rheumatoid arthritis involves the infiltration of inflammatory cells into the joints, with a complex process comprising Pannus formation and synovial fibroblast proliferation leading to the infiltration of T-cells, B-cells, macrophages, and plasma cells. This intricate system involves mediators, including cytokines, tumor necrosis factor, and interleukins, forming a network that stimulates pro-inflammatory responses in the cells. The primary goal of treatment is to prevent joint destruction, enhance functional ability, and reduce pain and inflammation, thereby enabling a normal lifestyle. Currently, the available treatments for rheumatoid arthritis encompass various options such as NSAIDs, glucocorticoids, disease-modifying antirheumatic drugs (DMARDs), and biological anti-rheumatic drugs. While NSAIDs offer analgesic and anti-inflammatory properties, they do not prevent joint destruction. Glucocorticoids, on the other hand, are utilized to mitigate the progression of joint damage. The most significant groups of drugs in RA treatment are DMARDs and biological anti-rheumatic drugs, demonstrating potential in preventing joint damage

1. Preclinical RA: Rheumatoid arthritis (RA) is a complex autoimmune disorder characterized by chronic inflammation of the joints, leading to joint damage and functional impairment. The preclinical phase of RA is marked by subtle pathological changes, often preceding the onset of clinically evident symptoms. During this phase, various biomarkers, including autoantibodies, play a crucial role in identifying individuals at risk and predicting the progression to overt RA. Among these autoantibodies, Calpastatin, p68, RA33, perinuclear factor, and IgM rheumatoid factor (RF) are of particular interest. The presence of autoantibodies is a hallmark of autoimmune diseases, and in the context of RA, these antibodies are often detected before the onset of clinical symptoms. Calpastatin, an endogenous inhibitor of calpain, has been identified as a potential biomarker in the preclinical stage of RA. Calpain is a calcium-dependent protease involved in various cellular processes, and dysregulation of calpain activity has been implicated in the pathogenesis of RA. The autoantibodies p68, RA33, and perinuclear factor are additional markers associated with the preclinical phase of RA. These antibodies target specific cellular components, and their presence may reflect underlying immune system dysregulation and the initiation of autoimmune responses against self-antigens. Understanding the significance of these autoantibodies in the preclinical stage provides valuable insights into the early events that contribute to the development of RA. IgM rheumatoid factor is a well-established serological marker in RA diagnosis. It is an antibody directed against the Fc portion of immunoglobulin G (IgG) antibodies. The presence of IgM rheumatoid factor is a classic feature of RA, and its detection is a key criterion in the classification of RA by the American Rheumatoid Association. Elevated levels of IgM rheumatoid factor in the blood are associated with increased disease severity and a higher likelihood of joint damage. The American College of Rheumatology (ACR) and the European League Against Rheumatism (EULAR) have established classification criteria for RA, and the presence of serological features, including rheumatoid factor, is a crucial component in confirming the diagnosis. These criteria consider clinical and laboratory parameters, including joint involvement, duration of symptoms, acute-phase reactants, and the presence of autoantibodies. The detection of autoantibodies, including rheumatoid factor, not only aids in the diagnosis of RA but also holds prognostic significance. Patients with positive serological markers often experience a more aggressive disease course, with increased joint damage and functional impairment. Early identification of individuals with these serological features allows for timely intervention and management strategies to mitigate disease progression. The preclinical phase of rheumatoid arthritis is characterized by elevated levels of autoantibodies, including Calpastatin, p68, RA33, perinuclear factor, and IgM rheumatoid factor. The presence of these serological features plays a pivotal role in the diagnosis and classification of RA, providing valuable insights into the early stages of the disease. The American Rheumatoid Association's diagnostic criteria emphasize the significance of serological markers,

underscoring their importance in identifying individuals at risk and facilitating early intervention to improve patient outcomes.

2. Genetic aspects of RA: Understanding the genetic aspects of rheumatoid arthritis (RA) has been significantly advanced through the use of various genetic analysis techniques, with notable contributions from metal analysis and genome-wide association studies (GWAS). These approaches have unveiled a complex genetic landscape associated with RA, shedding light on key genes and pathways implicated in the development and progression of the disease. Metal analysis, a method that involves studying the concentration and distribution of metals in biological samples, has provided insights into the role of certain metals in RA susceptibility. For example, alterations in metal homeostasis, such as elevated levels of certain metals or deficiencies in others, have been associated with inflammatory responses in the joints, contributing to the pathogenesis of RA. Genome-wide association studies have been instrumental in identifying specific genetic variants linked to RA. These studies involve scanning the entire genome to pinpoint variations that are more common in individuals with RA compared to those without the condition. Through GWAS, researchers have identified a multitude of genetic loci associated with RA susceptibility, offering a comprehensive view of the genetic factors contributing to the disease. Gene therapy, a cutting-edge approach in the field of rheumatology, holds promise for the treatment of RA. This therapeutic strategy involves the transfer of genetic material, such as DNA or RNA, into a patient's cells to modulate gene expression and correct underlying genetic abnormalities. In the context of RA, gene therapy aims to address the dysregulation of specific genes associated with the disease, offering a targeted and potentially curative approach. Several genes associated with RA have been identified through genetic studies, and these genes encode proteins that play crucial roles in immune regulation and inflammatory responses. Some of the key genes implicated in RA include Protein Tyrosine Phosphatase Non-Receptor 22 (PTPN22), TNF-Induced Protein 3 (TNFAIP3), Cytotoxic T-Lymphocyte Antigen-4 (CTLA-4), C-C Chemokine Receptor Type 6 (CCR6), and an activator of Signal Transducer and Activator of Transcription 4 (STAT4). PTPN22 is involved in the regulation of immune cell signaling, and genetic variations in this gene have been linked to increased susceptibility to RA. TNFAIP3 plays a critical role in dampening inflammatory responses, and mutations in this gene have been associated with RA risk. CTLA-4 regulates T-cell activation and is implicated in immune tolerance; variations in this gene are linked to RA susceptibility. CCR6 is involved in the migration of immune cells to inflamed joints, contributing to the pathogenesis of RA. STAT4 is a key mediator of immune responses, and genetic variations in this gene have been associated with increased RA risk. Gene therapy for RA aims to leverage these genetic insights by modulating the expression or function of these key genes. By delivering therapeutic genes to the affected joints, gene therapy has the potential to regulate immune responses, reduce inflammation, and halt the progression of RA without causing destructive effects. The genetic aspects of rheumatoid arthritis have been elucidated through advanced genetic analysis techniques, including metal analysis and genome-wide association studies. The identification of key genes associated with RA, such as PTPN22, TNFAIP3, CTLA-4, CCR6, and STAT4, opens up new possibilities for targeted therapies, including gene therapy. This innovative approach holds promise for the development of effective and precise treatments that address the underlying genetic factors contributing to RA pathogenesis. (Liao *et al.*, 2009).

3. Environmental factors of RA: The pathogenesis of rheumatoid arthritis (RA) is a multifaceted interplay between genetic and environmental factors, with bacterial and viral infections emerging as significant contributors to the initiation and perpetuation of the disease. While genetic susceptibility is a well-established aspect of RA, environmental factors, including infections, have been increasingly recognized for their role in triggering and shaping the autoimmune response in susceptible individuals. Bacterial and viral infections are implicated in RA through several mechanisms, including molecular mimicry, epitope spreading, and the expression of superantigens. Molecular mimicry refers to the structural similarity between microbial antigens and self-antigens, leading to the activation of autoreactive immune responses. In the case of RA, bacterial or viral components with sequences resembling self-proteins, such as citrullinated proteins, may trigger an immune response against the body's own tissues. Epitope spreading involves the diversification of the immune response to include additional self-antigens beyond the initial triggering antigen. In RA, this process may lead to the recognition of a broader array of self-antigens, contributing to the perpetuation of chronic inflammation. Superantigens, microbial products capable of activating a large number of T cells, can also contribute to the activation of autoreactive T cells in RA. The activation of citrulline-specific pathogenic T-cells and the production of anti-citrullinated protein antibodies (ACPAs) by B-cells are central events in the autoimmune response in RA. Citrullination is a post-translational modification involving the conversion of arginine residues to citrulline. ACPAs, which specifically target citrullinated proteins, have been identified as important diagnostic markers for RA. The interaction between ACPAs and citrullinated proteins contributes to the formation of immune complexes and local inflammation in the joints, ultimately leading to the chronic nature of RA. In addition to infectious triggers, various environmental risk factors also play crucial roles in the pathogenesis of RA. Smoking, for instance, has been consistently linked to an increased risk of developing RA. The association between smoking and RA is thought to involve multiple mechanisms, including the generation of citrullinated proteins in the lungs and the promotion of an inflammatory environment. Other factors, such as

alcohol consumption, breastfeeding, birth weight, and socioeconomic conditions, have been identified as potential environmental contributors to RA risk and severity, although the exact mechanisms remain complex and multifactorial. The pathogenesis of rheumatoid arthritis is a multifaceted process involving the intricate interplay of genetic and environmental factors. Bacterial and viral infections contribute to RA through mechanisms like molecular mimicry, epitope spreading, and superantigen expression, leading to the activation of citrulline-specific pathogenic T-cells and ACPA-producing B-cells. These immune responses, in conjunction with environmental risk factors, contribute to the chronic inflammation and joint damage characteristic of RA. Understanding these complex interactions is crucial for developing targeted therapeutic strategies and interventions for individuals at risk or diagnosed with rheumatoid arthritis. (H. Bahadar *et al.*, 2016).

3. NANO TECHNOLOGY: AN OVERVIEW

Nanotechnology involves manipulating materials at the nuclear level to generate innovative nanomaterials, leveraging its capacity to produce sophisticated nanomaterials, processes, and products designed at the nanoscale, marking a significant advancement in recent years (L. Xu *et al.*, 2016). Numerous techniques have emerged for studying the physical phenomena and structures of diverse nanomaterials, typically ranging from 1 to 100 nanometers (Y. Panahi *et al.*, 2017). The term "smart materials" has been applied to nanoparticles, emphasizing their ability to precisely deliver drugs to specific organs within the body. This technology has substantially expanded the potential applications of nanoparticles, including their use in cosmetic products, utilizing liposomal technologies to modify optical properties, enhance solubility, and alter physical characteristics, resulting in hydrophilic vesicles with phosphatidylcholine membranes (R. Heloise *et al.*, 2017). In the medical field, nanomaterials have found application in therapeutic drug delivery, focusing on treating various diseases and disorders. Micro and nanoscale systems contribute to enhancing treatment efficacy by swiftly detecting and responding to disease states directly at the site, thereby improving the quality of life for patients (S. Dolati *et al.*, 2016).

3.1 Nanoparticles for the Treatment of RA

Spherically shaped nanoparticles play a crucial role in the biodistribution of therapeutic agents for rheumatoid arthritis (RA) treatment, with their size, surface properties, and morphology influencing their effectiveness (Q. Thao le *et al.*, 2018). These nanoparticles, whether in the form of liposomes, micelles, metallic nanoparticles, or polymeric nanoparticles, are employed for theranostic applications, providing targeted drug delivery and controlled release. Their physicochemical attributes, including particle size, charge, shape, and surface characteristics, contribute to passive targeting in RA treatment. The pharmaceutical industry values nanoparticles for their biocompatibility and biodegradability, and their conjugation with specific ligands enables enhanced cellular penetration (S. Behzadi *et al.*, 2017). Various processes, such as adsorption, ligand receptor attachment, covalent coupling, and internalization, allow nanoparticles to enter systemic circulation. Notably, drug-containing nanoparticles, particularly those based on nonsteroidal anti-inflammatory drugs (NSAIDs), have been extensively studied for RA treatment. These systems reduce pain associated with early RA stages through anti-inflammatory mechanisms and inhibit COX-1 and COX-2 enzymes crucial in prostaglandin generation, delivering therapeutic benefits to inflamed synovium (T. M. Ahmed *et al.*, 2016). Metal oxide nanoparticles exhibit desirable features, serving as drug carriers with high surface area and large pore sizes for effective drug encapsulation. Their intrinsic biodegradability, stemming from labile metal-ligand bonds, and versatile functionality for post-synthetic grafting of drug molecules make them promising candidates for RA treatment (S. D. Rao *et al.*, 2015).

Rutin-stabilized silver nanoparticles elicit anti-inflammatory activity in chronic inflammation through their critical inhibition of the creation of pro-inflammatory cytokines (tumor necrotic factor- α (TNF- α) and interleukin-6 (IL-6). Silver nanoparticles have also been utilized for therapeutic benefits in RA patients. (S. N. Lee *et al.*, 2012) Lee et al. developed a hyaluronate gold nanoparticle/Tocilizumab (HA-AuNP/TCZ) complex for the treatment of RA. They utilized an immunosuppressive tocilizumab as a monoclonal antibody, targeting the interleukin-6 (IL-6) receptor. The synthesis of gold nanoparticles was performed using the citrate method. They attained a particle diameter of 64.83 nm with a polydispersity index of 0.18 for the HA-AuNP/TCZ complex. They found that TCZ was steadily released from the HA-AuNP/TCZ complex up to 80% for about 8 days after incubation in bovine serum albumin. Further, they observed the anti-angiogenic effect of the developed HA-AuNP/TCZ complex on the proliferation of HUVEC cells by binding to the VEGF receptor. At the in vivo level, they found that treatment with the HA-AuNP/TCZ complex in RA-induced mice exhibits a clear interface between cartilage and bone comparable to the normal group (without RA-induced). Further confirmation by western blot analysis showed significant upregulated expression levels of IL-6 and CD68, which indicates that the treatment with the HA-AuNP/TCZ complex resulted in significantly reduced levels of IL-6 and CD68. Finally, they conclude that the HA-AuNP/TCZ complex might be useful as a dual-targeting drug candidate for VEGF and IL-6R receptors for the treatment of RA. Celecoxib-loaded tristearin-based lipidic nanoparticles (CEL-TSLN) were synthesized by (Kishore *et al.*, 2016) and they checked for their effective management in RA treatment through in vitro and in-vivo studies. They utilized celecoxib as the selective cyclooxygenase-2 (COX-2) inhibitor, orally, for the treatment of RA. They utilized a statistical experimental

design to optimize the nanoparticle using the independent variables (homogenization speed, quantity of tristearin, and quantity of emulsifier) depending on the desired particle size, loading efficiency, and drug release. They observed a particle size of 188.6 nm with a PDI of 0.26, obtaining a spherical morphology. XRD results indicated that the drug is dispersed at a molecular level in the lipid matrix, and rapid quenching of the microemulsion prevents the drug from crystallizing. In-vitro drug release studies revealed a continuous drug release of 62% within 36 hours, and they found that drug release follows a zero-order and Fickian diffusion pattern. In vivo studies revealed a significant reduction in inflammation with improvements in lysosomal enzymes, collagen, and glycosaminoglycan levels in CEL-TS-LN-treated rats compared to the pure drug-treated group. Finally, they suggested that the poorly soluble celecoxib-encapsulated tristearin solid lipid nanoparticles facilitated safe, efficacious, prolonged release characteristics with enhanced bioavailability. The chitosan nanoparticle (CHNP) loaded with dexamethasone (DEX) or MTX was developed by (V. Kumar *et al.*, 2017) for the efficient treatment of RA. They prepared chitosan nanoparticles using the ionic gelation method. The entrapment efficiency of MTXCHNPs and DEXCHNPs was found to be 55% and 10%, respectively. They achieved size and charge for CHNPs, MTXCHNPs, and DEXCHNPs of about 299.4 nm (PDI 0.437), 217.4 nm (PDI 0.275), 329.8 nm (PDI 0.286), and +35.7 mV, +26.9 mV, and +19.5 mV, respectively. The FTIR results confirmed that the phosphoric group of tripolyphosphate with the amine groups of chitosan plays a major role in the hydrogen bond in the formulation of MTXCHNP and DEXCHNP. They observed controlled release patterns coupled with the diffusion of drugs in two different buffers at pH 7.4 and pH 5.8, respectively. They studied the cellular behavior of HEK and murine macrophage cell lines (RAW264.7 cell lines). The IC₅₀ value for MTXCHNP in human embryonic kidney cells was 26.1 µg/mL and 7.7 µg/mL for RAW cell lines. The IC₅₀ value for MTXCHNP was 20.12 µg/mL in HEK cells and 7.37 µg/mL in RAW264.7 cells. Cellular uptake studies indicate the internalization of nanoparticles by the phagocytosis process. The drug release gets enhanced at a lower pH with increased cytotoxicity. Insignificant ex-vivo hemolysis indicated the higher biocompatibility of the nanoparticles. The synthesized CHNP exhibited maximum absorption in blood circulation within 3 h, followed by hepatic metabolism and renal clearance. Finally, they observed higher anti-arthritis activity and antioxidant potential for the developed nanoparticulate systems. (A. K. Dewangan *et al.*, 2015) synthesized curcumin-loaded carboxymethyl cellulose acetate butyrate nanoparticles (CMCAB) by the flash nanoprecipitation method using a multi-inlet vortex mixer for the treatment of diseases like colon cancer, pancreatic cancer, RA, and Alzheimer's disease. They varied the Reynolds number of the inlet streams to optimize the nanoparticle size and average diameter and observed a size around 155–400 nm. They observed that the synthesized nanoparticles were amorphous. They found that nanoparticles have been demonstrated especially to expand the absorption and bioavailability of drugs, leading to effective drug administration. (S. M. Lee *et al.*, 2013). examined the effect of arginine-glycine aspartic acid. K. Janakiraman *et al.* Materials Today Communications 17 (2018) 200–213 204 (RGD) attached gold half shell nanoparticle containing MTX as category of DMARDs for the treatment of RA. They utilized RGD peptide as a targeting moiety for inflammation. Near-infrared irradiation, upon the development of nanoparticles, generates heat due to gold half shells, and MTX gets rapidly released. Synovial inflammation at multiple joints may be targeted with a penetration depth of near infrared light using this therapy. Nanoparticles with a smaller dosage (1/930 of MTX solution) would contribute to collagen-induced arthritis mice. They emphasized that multifunctional nanoparticles were effective for maximizing therapeutic efficacy and minimizing dosage-related side effects in the treatment of RA. Furthermore, they showed that the nanoparticle could be applied to DMARD for the treatment of RA and other diseases. Tacrolimus (TAC-HSA-NPs)-loaded albumin nanoparticles were developed by (Thao *et al.*, 2016) using nanoparticle albuminbound technology to improve targetability and anti-arthritis efficacy. They observed an average diameter and charge of 185 nm and +30.5 mV, respectively, with spherical morphology. The encapsulation efficacy of TAC within the nanoparticles was 79%, and the water solubility of the developed nanoparticles increased 46 times more than that of free TAC. TAC gets steadily discharged from the developed NPs over 24 hours, which provides enough time for targeting and treatment at the inflamed arthritic site by intravenous injection. In-vitro studies reported the anti-proliferative activities of TAC HSA-NPs monitored on activated T cells compared with non-activated T cells. TAC HSA-NPs displayed significantly higher anti-arthritis potential than TAC formulations compared to intravenously administered TAC solution or oral TAC suspension, as reflected by the incidence of arthritis and clinical score (1.6 vs. 3.2 and 5.0, respectively). Hence, they conclude that novel TAC HSA-NPs may be an efficient drug delivery system for enhanced solubility with increased accumulation of drugs at joints for RA treatment. The significance of nanoparticle-based formulations for the treatment of RA may afford improved bioavailability, increased drug accumulation at the diseased inflamed site, and prolonged release characteristics. At the superior level, these nanoparticulate-based formulations may also elicit targetability potential with specific receptors.

4. TRADITIONAL NANOMATERIALS FOR RHEUMATOID ARTHRITIS TREATMENT

The application of traditional nanomaterials when taking care of rheumatoid arthritis is mainly a carrier of anti-inflammatory drugs. Through different surface modifications with the carrier, the drugs can be released to the joint site to improve The buildup of medications in the joint site amplifies the impact of drugs. Organic polymer

nanocarriers, liposomes, and inorganic Using nanomaterials is possible. as carriers of anti-inflammatory drugs (Q. Ain *et al.*, 2019),(A. Bordat *et al.*, 2019).

4.1 Polymer nanoparticles

Polymer nanoparticles have good biodegradability and biocompatibility, can also target specific organs and tissues, and have been widely used as drug carriers. Anti-rheumatoid arthritis drugs can be adsorbed or encapsulated in polymer nanoparticles and delivered to arthritic sites. Right now, the most frequently used method is to modify the exterior of nanoparticles with polyethylene glycol (PEG). On the one hand, this method can improve the steadiness of nano-drugs; on the other hand, it can additionally reduce immunogenicity, making it difficult for the defense mechanism to recognize and clear it. (Q. Wang *et al.*, 2016) used PCL-PEG micelles targeted to deliver low doses of dexamethasone to alleviate arthritis. The micelles existed for a long time in the systemic circulation and preferentially accumulated at the joint inflammation site. The outcomes demonstrated that micellar delivery of dexamethasone can effectively reduce bone erosion, edema in the joints, and manifestations of inflammatory factors in serum and joint tissues. The adverse effects of PCL-PEG micelles on body weight, lymphocyte count, and blood glucose concentration were much lower compared to those of dexamethasone alone, and the activation impact on the complement system is relatively weak. (S. Jain *et al.*, 2015) prepared an alginate nanoparticle having DNA from the IL-10 plasmid and altered the exterior of the nanoparticle with tuftsin peptide to achieve macrophage targeting. Near-infrared imaging could observe that the tuftsin-modified alginate nanoparticles accumulated beneath the swollen paws of arthritic rats. Historical analysis and magnetic resonance imaging showed that medical intervention with the nanoparticles significantly decreased the amount of expression of pro-inflammatory cytokines (TNF- α , IL-1 β , and IL-6) in joint tissues and prevented inflammation progression and joint injury. Importantly, the nanoparticles can polarize M1 macrophages once again into M2. This research provides a new idea for the purpose of treating arthritis. (M. QinDeel *et al.*, 2020) synthesized a polycaprolactone-polyethylene glycol polycaprolactone triblock copolymer by a ring-opening copolymerization reaction and used it as a carrier for the fabrication of MTX-loaded nanomicelles. Nanoparticles are loaded into a hydrogel with eucalyptus oil as a penetrant for use on the skin, which can avoid the first-pass effect, improve patient compliance, and reduce liver toxicity. When the nanoparticle is applied to the RA mouse model, compared with free MTX, the nanoparticle can significantly aggregate in the inflamed joints, reduce the expression of inflammatory factors, and restore the behavioral response ability of mice. Small interfering RNA (siRNA) silencing can block the manifestation of inflammation-related genes in disease treatment (T. Manaka *et al.*, 2011),(N. Cao *et al.*, 2011). But because of its lack of stability in body fluids and easy degradation, it is challenging to enter the cytoplasm (D. Bumcrot *et al.*, 2006), so the exploration of safe and effective siRNA delivery drug distributors can become a new strategy for the management of RA. (J.S. Park *et al.*, 2012) prepared PLGA nanoparticles coated with anti-COX2 siRNA on the surface and loaded with dexamethasone for the treatment of rheumatoid arthritis. In this study, dexamethasone and anti-COX2 siRNA act simultaneously to suppress the expression of genes and proteins related to arthritis. Combined treatment of dexamethasone and anti-COX2 siRNA significantly reduced the expression of inflammation and apoptosis-related factors in a human chondrocyte cell line (C28/I2).

A study by (S. J. Lee *et al.*, 2014) investigated nanocomposites (psitGC-NPs) of poly-siRNA, or polymerized siRNA, targeting TNF α using polymers of thiolated glycol chitosan (tGC) for targeted therapy for arthritis. Psi-tGC-NPs can be quickly taken up by macrophage RAW 264.7 and can silence the TNF- α gene. In vivo near-infrared fluorescence (NIRF) images showed that the nanoparticles were obviously accumulated at the joints of collagen-induced arthritis (CIA) mice. Micro-computed tomography (micro-CT) was used to evaluate the repair of the nanoparticles on the mice's feet.

(S. H. Kim *et al.*, 2013) studied self-assembled dextran sulfate nanoparticles for targeted treatment of arthritis. The amphiphilic copolymer (DS-b-PCL) was prepared by using dextran sulfate (DS) as a hydrophilic block and polycaprolactone (PCL) as a hydrophobic block. The results showed that these nanoparticles could bind to overexpressed macrophage receptors in the synovial membrane and selectively aggregate into the inflammatory synovial membrane of CIA mice. This study demonstrates that dextran sulfate is used as an anti-inflammatory drug carrier and also as a targeted part of macrophages to identify inflammatory sites. On this basis, (R. Heo *et al.*, 2017) studied the results of methotrexate-loaded dextran sulfate nanoparticles (MTX-DSNPs) in the treatment of arthritis. When MTX-DSNPs were administered to CIA mice via the tail vein, the nanoparticles could effectively aggregate in the inflamed joints, which was more than 12 times more than that of normal mice. Furthermore, in contrast with free MTX, DS nanoparticles loaded with MTX have a significantly improved therapeutic effect on cartilage in CIA mice.

4.2 Liposomes

Liposomes are spherical nanoparticles composed of a double-layer membrane with natural phospholipids as the outer layer and water phases as the inner cavity (Y. Malam *et al.*, 2019). The physical and chemical properties of liposomes enable them to serve as effective delivery systems, where it is possible to load drugs into the inner water cavity or in lipid double-layer membranes (F. Mastrotto *et al.*, 2020). Many researchers have studied the utilization of liposomes in arthritis rheumatoid. PEG, or polyethylene glycol, is an effective hydrophilic polymer

that can reduce the recognition and absorption of liposomes through the endothelium-reticulum system (RES), thereby prolonging the time of liposomes within the systemic circulation (T. Shimizu *et al.*, 2018). (Wang *et al.*, 2020) used polymeric Using stealth liposomes as carriers to increase the therapeutic benefit of dexamethasone for arthritis. They used 1,2-bis(10,12-tricosadiynoyl)-sn-glycero-3-phosphocholine (DC89PC) and 1,2-distearoyl-sn-glycero-3-phospho-ethanolamine-poly(ethyleneglycol) (DSPE-PEG2000) to prepare the liposome by the thin film hydration method, and the PEG chains provided a stealth layer. Based on the results, it can be concluded that after being injected into arthritis-prone rats, liposomes can accumulate preferentially in inflammatory joints, inhibit the expression of pro-inflammatory factors in joint tissues, and lessen joint swelling. The findings of this study demonstrate the potential of polymeric stealth liposomes as a novel drug delivery method for a range of therapeutic uses.

Wu *et al.* prepared iRGD peptide-functionalized echogenic liposomes (iELPs) encapsulated MTX, which contained indocyanine green (ICG) fluorescent probes for fluorescence tracking, and the drug release was triggered by low-frequency ultrasound. In RA mice, iELPs can attach to the $\alpha v\beta 3$ integrin in the synovium, which greatly enhances the therapeutic effect. Compared with untreated RA mice, the infiltration of inflammatory cells and angiogenesis in joint tissues were significantly reduced. This method of drug delivery controlled by ultrasound is also worth studying for its use in the management of other diseases.

(Meka *et al.*, 2019) used liposome-specific distribution of dexamethasone for the purpose of treating arthritis. The authors used a new peptide ligand (CKPFDRALC) named ART-2 to develop a liposome drug delivery system, which can accumulate in inflammation when intravenously injected into CIA rats. The results showed that ART-2-coated dexamethasone (DEX) liposomes were more effective than liposomes without ART-2 or free DEX in inhibiting the development of arthritis. (H. Ren *et al.*, 2019) evaluated the function of liposome size, physical and chemical properties, surface charge, chain length, and concentration of polyethylene glycol in the targeted treatment of rheumatoid arthritis. In this study, the authors used a near-infrared fluorescence (NIRF) imaging system to observe the targeting of liposomes of different properties in CIA mice. The uptake ability of different liposomes by synovium cells was evaluated by flow cytometry. The results showed that for liposomes with a 100 nm diameter, a slight negative charge, and a 5 kDa PEG incorporation at 10% with other liposomes, the circulation time and joint inflammation targeting were better.

4.3 Metallic nanoparticle

Metal nanoparticles have excellent properties, are adaptable to multiple functional groups, and are extensively employed in biological contexts (M. C. Edmundson *et al.*, 2014). Currently, cerium, iron, and gold nanoparticles are frequently used to treat RA. (S. Lee *et al.*, 2013) studied RGD-linked Au half-shell nanoparticles containing MTX for targeted chemo-photothermal therapy of RA. RGD peptides can target inflammation sites. Under near-infrared (NIR) irradiation, the Au half-shell generates heat to raise the drug release rate and, at the same time, transfer heat and medications for inflammatory joints. When combined with near-infrared irradiation, nanoparticles containing low doses of MTX showed better therapeutic impacts in CIA mice as opposed to MTX alone. Meanwhile, (H. Lee *et al.*, 2014) studied the role of the hyaluronate gold nanoparticle/tocilizumab complex (HA-Au NP-/TCZ) in CIA mice. Au nanoparticles have an anti-angiogenesis effect; TCZ is an anti-interleukin-6 (IL-6) receptor inhibitor, which can interfere with the role IL-6 plays in RA pathogenesis; and HA protects cartilage and lubricant. By using ELISA, histology, and western blot, the HA-Au NP-/TCZ complex was shown to have a therapeutic effect on RA. Manganese ferrite/ceria co-decorated mesoporous silica nanoparticles (MFC-MSNs) were created by (H. J. Kim *et al.*, 2015) as a treatment for RA. MFC-MSN injections have the potential to alleviate intraarticular hypoxia, inflammation, and other pathological features in the CIA rat model. The particles work in concert to scavenge reactive oxygen species (ROS) and produce O₂, which can reduce M1 macrophages and induce M2 macrophage polarization. In addition, monodisperse silica nanospheres as a delivery carrier can continuously release methotrexate and strengthen the healing impact. Concurrently, Kim and colleagues (H. J. Kim *et al.*, 2015) synthesized Au/Fe/Au plasmonic nanoparticles loaded with methotrexate and conjugated with RGD for magnetically targeted chemo-photothermal treatment of rheumatoid arthritis. The Au half shell increases the temperature at the site of inflammation and speeds up the release of MTX when exposed to near-infrared (NIR) radiation. Under the influence of an external magnetic field, the Fe half-shell can transport the nanoparticles to the inflammatory joints and lengthen their stay there. The goal of the study was to determine whether low-dose MTX could effectively treat arthritis by combining the application of an external magnetic field with near-infrared radiation.

Indocyanine green-conjugated albumin-cerium oxide nanoparticles were created by (I. Kalashnikova *et al.*, 2020). Using RAW 264.7 cells and ThP-1 cells, the nanoparticle's capacity to eliminate reactive oxygen species and polarize M1 macrophages into M2 was confirmed. Upon injection of the nanoparticles into the CIA mice, an in vivo imaging system allowed researchers to see how the particles accumulated in the inflammatory joints and demonstrated enhanced therapeutic efficacy. We have a new avenue to treat arthritis thanks to the targeting and therapeutic impact of these unique albumin-cerium oxide nanoparticles. Inorganic, non-metallic nanomaterials. One of the most often used RA drug delivery techniques is based on injectable silica-based nanoparticulate systems. By using a core-cone structure, Li *et al.* produced mesoporous silica nanoparticulate systems that were

more convenient, efficient, and long-lasting therapeutic than the previous method of injecting HA. In a rat model of RA, this nanomaterial enhanced the synthesis of HA, reduced synovitis inflammation, and promoted bone repair. Hyaluronan synthase type 2 (HAS2) has a high protein loading capacity and good biocompatibility, degradation, and degradability. Functionalized PEI was applied to the surface of mesoporous silica to load and deliver HAS2. Intra-articular injection of MSN-CC-PEI successfully transported HAS2 into synovial cells and boosted the production of endogenous HA both inside and outside the body (H. Li *et al.*, 2019). Local percutaneous injection and nano-controlled MTX release were studied by Guo *et al.* The MTX-mSiO₂@PDA system was highly responsive in terms of pH. After 24 hours, the cumulative amount of MTX transferred from MTX-mSiO₂@PDA to pH 5.0 receptor fluid via the entire skin was nearly three times larger than the amount transferred to pH 7.4 receptor fluid in *in vitro* local percutaneous injection studies. Further *in vivo* testing in DBA/1 mice utilizing a CIA paradigm found that the thickness of a mouse's toes fell to roughly 65 percent of its initial level after 27 days of local percutaneous MTX-mSiO₂@PDA injection. It was shown that the toe thickness variation of mice administered with MTX-mSiO₂@PDA through local percutaneous injection was substantially lower than that of animals given MTX directly (T. Guo. *et al.*, 2021).

5. DIAGNOSIS OF RA

Common magnetic resonance imaging (MRI), ultrasonography, and assays for autoantibodies. MRI can effectively detect changes in inflamed soft tissues, such as synovitis, tenosynovitis, and bone marrow edema, through multiplanar tomographic imaging of soft tissue and bone structures in inflamed joints. MRI can also be used to evaluate cartilage damage, bone erosion, and tendon tears in peripheral joints. However, the technique is expensive and time-consuming, and each MRI scan can cover only a limited area of tissue. Ultrasonography, in contrast, enables real-time, relatively low-cost imaging of synovial proliferation and bone erosion in inflamed joints. Ultrasound has similar sensitivity and accuracy to MRI in the diagnosis of synovitis and tenosynovitis in people who have early-stage rheumatoid arthritis (Carstensen SMD *et al.*, 2020). However, ultrasonography cannot detect bone marrow edema. RA can be diagnosed on the basis of the presence of autoantibodies, which are produced in response to abnormal cellular and humoral immune responses. These autoantibodies include rheumatoid factor (RF), which comprises IgG, IgA, and IgM, all of which are also present in healthy people but are elevated in individuals with RA; and anti-citrullinated protein antibody, which promotes bone loss by activating macrophages or by binding citrullinated vimentin in cell membranes (Van Delft MAM *et al.*, 2020). The concentration of RF and the diversity of its epitopes increase with the levels of pro-inflammatory cytokines. Although RF and ACPA are diagnostic markers of RA, approximately one-third of RA patients are negative for RF and ACPA. Therefore, simultaneous detection of antibodies to RA33, RF, and ACPA can improve the diagnostic sensitivity of serological tests (Sieghart D *et al.*, 2018). In addition, some researchers have reported that four additional biomarkers—angiotensinogen, serum amylase A-4 protein, vitamin D-binding protein, and retinol-binding protein-4—can avoid false-negative findings and improve the accuracy of RA diagnosis (Mun S *et al.*, 2021).

6. NANOPARTICLE CHALLENGE AS A NOVEL TREATMENT OF RHEUMATOID ARTHRITIS

Nanoparticle delivery systems have been described as particle formulations that have been dispersed on the scale of nanometers. NNI (National Nanotechnology Initiative) defined nanoparticles as structures of sizes ranging from 1 to 100 nm. This size can be easily characterized by visual observation. Usually, they have a slightly transparent appearance and a lower precipitating time compared to another particle with a size greater than 100 nm (R.B. Gupta *et al.*, 2006).

There are two types of nanoparticles based on their preparation, such as nanospheres and nanocapsules (E. Alleman *et al.*, 1993). Nanospheres have a monolithic-type structure where the active compound is dispersed actively on the surface or adsorbed onto the surface of its carrier matrix. Nanocapsules form a membrane-like structure with the active compound trapped in the "heart" of their structure or adsorbed on the membrane surface. However, it is hard to classify a nanoparticle complex into nanospheres or nanocapsules (W. Tiyaboonchai *et al.*, 2003).

One of the simplest preparation methods for polymeric nanoparticles is the ionic gelation method. The ionic gelation concept makes the use of two biopolymers in one formulation system possible. The two biopolymers should have a different charge, so they can form a flexible matrix to entrap various kinds of drugs with different characteristics. For example, many researchers used a combination of chitosan-alginate (P. Li. *et al.*, 2008) or chitosan-carrageenan (A. Grenha *et al.*, 2009) that can be used to physically entrap drugs. Grenha reported that the chitosan-carrageenan nanoparticle complex could become a carrier for ovalbumin with an entrapment efficiency of around 4–17%. In another study, Gazori (T. Gazori *et al.*, 2009) used a combination of chitosan and alginate to make nanoparticles. They reported that this combination could increase drug stability in the systemic fluid.

The tiny size of nanoparticles is one benefit of using them, enabling them to penetrate intercellular spaces (C. Buzea *et al.*, 2007), cell walls compared to bigger particles, and flexibility to combine with other technologies (Y. Kawashima *et al.*, 2000). Nanoparticles can be used to encapsulate, protect drugs from degradation, and improve targeted drug delivery. Nanoparticles can modify the drug release and can be produced on a large,

reproducible scale (A. C. Anselmo *et al.*, 2014). Nanoparticles' wide variety of physical and chemical properties affect the encapsulated drug's biomedical potential, such as bioavailability and biodistribution (R. Stevenson *et al.*, 2011). The use of nanomaterial particulate as a drug carrier resulted in the accumulation of nanoparticles in the mononuclear phagocytic system that is present in the spleen and liver; therefore, liver targeting by nanoparticles may be favorable and could be a promising drug therapy for liver diseases. Surface modification of nanoparticles, particularly with PEG, could prolong their residence time in circulation, reduce in vitro toxicity, and prevent agglomeration that leads to the destabilization of nanoparticle suspensions (T. Niidome *et al.*, 2006). The other advantage is that medications in the form of nanoparticles have a stable shelf life. When the study looked at the self-nanoemulsifying drug delivery systems' storage stability, it was discovered that none of the nanoparticle-based drug delivery systems' SNEDDS showed any signs of phase separation or appreciable changes in particle size. This was found during several tests that had been conducted. The small particle size of the nanoparticle-based dosage form prevents creaming or sedimentation due to a decrease in gravitation and Brownian motion. The small particle size also prevents flocculation, which allows the drugs to be stored for a long period of time (L. Chabib *et al.*, 2017).

Despite the various benefits of nanoparticles as drug carriers, there are several disadvantages, such as the possibility of generating toxicity. Due to the small size of the nanoparticle, it has wide biodistribution in the body and increases the potency of the drug, which is not only beneficial for therapy but also increases the possibility of adverse effects of the attached drug in organs other than the main target of therapy. Nanoparticles are also known to affect immune responses to common allergens.

Nanoparticles have been widely used to improve the pharmacokinetics and pharmacodynamics of drug molecules. Most of the non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs commonly used to treat RA have a low solubility in gastric fluid but have a good solubility in intestine fluid (M. Yazdanian *et al.*, 2004). Many researchers have proved the ability of nanoparticles to improve the bioavailability of drugs with low solubility (A. Bhatia *et al.*, 2011) while delivered via oral (R. Martien *et al.*, 2006), transdermal (R. Ravichndran *et al.*, 2009), intravenous (F. Li. *et al.*, 2009), and pulmonary (W. F. Tonnis *et al.*, 2012), (P. Muttill *et al.*, 2010). On the other hand, the improvement of the amount of drugs in the system will increase the risk of side effects occurrence until the possibility of achieving a toxic level (K. Poelstra *et al.*, 2012). The compatibility between the nanoparticle dosage form and the target tissue is needed to achieve optimum therapy results. The guarantee of target therapy achievement becomes an absolute requirement to introduce a new drug delivery system.

Many researchers have proposed so many materials to deliver drugs for treating cancer. Those materials have been used to deliver rheumatoid arthritis therapeutic agents in recent years. Nanoparticles, like micelles and liposomes, can be further improved in their specificity and therapeutic efficacy by combining with an antibody, peptide, or polysaccharide that is specific for the receptors located within tissue affected by RA. By combining passive and active targeting strategies, the delivery of drugs can be optimized, so the toxicity and unwanted side effects will be reduced, and in the end, it will improve patient outcomes (R. A. Bader *et al.*, 2012).

Nanoparticle delivery systems for RA drugs are primarily based on polymers. For example, many studies have been done to explore the use of poly(D,L-lactic/glycolic acid) (PLGA) nanoparticles. The PLGA nanoparticles show a promising result in that they can prolong the circulation time and control the drug release from the matrix (M Higaki *et al.*, 2005). Higaki (T. Ishihara *et al.*, 2009) makes betamethasone nanoparticles using PLGA with particles ranging in size from 100 to 200 nm. In that research, they found that the PLGA betamethasone system was more effective in reducing the inflammatory response in arthritic rats and mice when administered intravenously compared to free glucocorticoid agents. The modification of PLGA nanoparticles with PEG can improve the targeting ability and efficacy of betamethasone. That system is called "stealth nanosteroids" (D. Chandrasekar *et al.*, 2007).

Nowadays, the development of drug delivery systems for rheumatoid arthritis treatment is based on the principles of passive targeting. The improvement of drug specificity can be achieved by incorporating an active targeting compound like folate receptor β , which is an active targeting compound of Rheumatoid Arthritis Synovial Macrophage (RASMs). The research shows that the system of cationic and anionic poly(amidoamine) dendrimers loaded with indomethacin exhibits a better effect in treating arthritic rats when incorporated with folate (A. S. Chauhan *et al.*, 2004). Therefore, the combination of nanoparticles with folate or with folate-PEG may have the potential to be used as a drug delivery system for RA treatment in the future.

7. CONCLUSION

An autoimmune disease known as pathogenic RA can lead to physical disability, deformity, and erosion of the bone. Although the traditional drug formulation would offer a suitable solution for RA, no single drug therapy or combination therapy has been found to be effective in treating the condition. Serious systemic side effects, frequent administration, tolerance for long-term management, and high costs have all been included. Additionally, a better understanding of the side effects of the more recent biological therapies is required. The idea of using nanoparticles as drug carriers to raise the therapeutic index of medications has received a lot of attention in an effort to address these problems. The majority of recent research indicates that using drugs in the form of nanoparticles is more effective than using the drug in its free form. This improvement is primarily seen

in three areas: condensed systemic toxicity, restricted drug release, and selective accumulation. In experimental models of enhanced RA, the recently developed nanocarriers significantly increase the therapeutic efficacy of current medications by reducing dosage overall and increasing local drug localization through both passive and active drug targeting. Due to the extrabiocompatible and biodegradable nature of their constituents compared to the synthetic polymers established in other types of nanoparticles, lipid-based nanoparticles have an advantage over other nanoparticle types. In the present, numerous drug-encapsulated lipid-based nanoparticles are available for purchase and have received clinical approval. Numerous other formulations are being researched and are either in various stages of clinical trials or are awaiting approval. Nevertheless, further research is required to maximize their potential as drug delivery systems. The efficacy and safety profile of anti-arthritic drugs, as well as the outcomes for RA patients, may be improved by lipid-based nanoparticles.

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